

“I’ve Heard of You!”: Generate Spoken Named Entity Recognition Data for Unseen Entities

Jiawei Yu^{1*}, Xiang Geng^{2*}, Yuang Li³, Mengxin Ren³, Wei Tang³, Jiahuan Li², Zhibin Lan¹,
Min Zhang³, Hao Yang³, Shujian Huang^{2†}, Jinsong Su^{1†}

¹School of Informatics, Xiamen University, China

²National Key Laboratory for Novel Software Technology, Nanjing University, China

³Huawei Translation Services Center, China

yujiawei@stu.xmu.edu.cn, gx@smail.nju.edu.cn, jssu@xmu.edu.cn
/liyuan3,zhangmin186,yanghao30/@huawei.com

Abstract—Spoken named entity recognition (NER) aims to identify named entities from speech, playing an important role in speech processing. New named entities appear every day, however, annotating their Spoken NER data is costly. In this paper, we demonstrate that existing Spoken NER systems perform poorly when dealing with previously unseen named entities. To tackle this challenge, we propose a method for generating Spoken NER data based on a named entity dictionary (NED) to reduce costs. Specifically, we first use a large language model (LLM) to generate sentences from the sampled named entities and then use a text-to-speech (TTS) system to generate the speech. Furthermore, we introduce a noise metric to filter out noisy data. To evaluate our approach, we release a novel Spoken NER benchmark along with a corresponding NED containing 8,853 entities. Experiment results show that our method achieves state-of-the-art (SOTA) performance in the in-domain, zero-shot domain adaptation, and fully zero-shot settings. Our data will be available at <https://github.com/DeepLearnXMU/HeardU>.

Index Terms—Spoken NER, large language model, data augmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

Spoken named entity recognition (NER) is the task of identifying and categorizing named entities from speech into pre-defined categories, such as person (PER), location (LOC), and organization (ORG) [1]. It is typically performed using either a pipeline system [2]–[5] or an end-to-end (E2E) system [6]–[9]. Spoken NER is crucial for grasping the meaning of speech and therefore has been widely applied, including protecting entity privacy [10] and correcting entity errors in automatic speech recognition (ASR) [11].

However, Spoken NER poses greater challenges than text NER. Speech varies greatly in pronunciation, accents, and dialects, significantly expanding the input space beyond that of text. Additionally, annotating Spoken NER data is more costly than annotating standard text NER data. Consequently, the availability of open-source Spoken NER datasets is limited, focusing on specific domains and languages [12]. Every day, numerous new entities are named, such as newly released products. Can existing Spoken NER methods recognize these unseen entities by using Spoken NER data from other domains?

Unfortunately, as illustrated in Figure 1, both pipeline and E2E Spoken NER methods show much poorer performance on unseen entities compared to seen entities.¹ Previous work, Un-Sp [13] attempts to generate Spoken NER data by distilling different Spoken NER models. However, this method highly relies on in-domain speech which is hard to acquire, and the noise of generated data is hard to measure. In this paper, we propose a novel framework named

Fig. 1. Both pipeline and E2E Spoken NER methods perform worse on unseen entities compared to seen entities. Our method works well, with greater improvement observed for unseen entities.

HeardU, which generates Spoken NER data based on the named entity dictionary (NED). Building the entity dictionary is much easier than acquiring Spoken NER data or in-domain speech. Moreover, the entity dictionary is off-the-shelf in many downstream applications, including terminology databases in machine translation [14], [15] and name sets in dialogue generation [16].

The HeardU pipeline is presented in the Figure 2. To construct a NED effectively, we employ a general-domain NER model to recognize entities within the in-domain documents and ask the large language model (LLM) or human annotators to refine the recognized entities. Next, we sample multiple entities from the NED and instruct the LLM to generate coherent contextual information based on these selected entities and their respective types. Finally, we feed the generated text into a general-domain text-to-speech (TTS) model to synthesize the corresponding speech output. We analyze the noise source of the generated Spoken NER data and propose a noise metric to identify low-quality data.

For evaluation, we introduce a new benchmark for Spoken NER in Chinese, named ST-CMDS-NER, along with its associated human-refined NED. Experiment results show that HeardU achieves state-of-the-art (SOTA) results across different settings. Using the LLM-refined NED in English, HeardU achieves F1 score increases of 2.76%, 19.76%, and 18.33% in the in-domain, zero-shot domain adaptation, and fully zero-shot settings, respectively. Using the human-refined NED in Chinese, HeardU achieves F1 score increases of 32.98% and 9.66% in the zero-shot domain adaptation and fully zero-shot settings, respectively.

Overall, our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We show that existing Spoken NER methods fail to handle

* denotes equal contribution to this work.

† Corresponding author

¹Unseen entities are defined as those that appear in the target domain test set, but not in the general-domain training set.

Fig. 2. The HeardU framework.

unseen entities and highlight that building the NED is more feasible than acquiring Spoken NER data.

- We release a new Spoken NER benchmark in Chinese and its corresponding NED for zero-shot domain adaptation and fully zero-shot settings.
- We propose the HeardU framework to generate Spoken NER data by using the NED, LLM, and TTS model, and to identify and filter out low-quality data.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Task Formulation

In Spoken NER, an instance is generally represented as a triplet $\{X, Y, Z\}$. Here, X refers to the spoken utterance, $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$ represents its transcription with n tokens, and $Z = \{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n\}$ denotes the associated BIO tags. For BIO tags [17], B- t and I- t indicate the beginning and inner tokens of an entity categorized as type t , where t belongs to a pre-defined set of entity types $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$. O represents tokens that do not belong to any named entity.

B. Named Entity Dictionary

As discussed before, many downstream tasks already have an NED. This section shows that constructing an NED from scratch is much more efficient and cost-effective than creating Spoken NER datasets, making HeardU adaptable to various scenarios. Inspired by AISHELL-NER [8], we use a text NER model for automatic NED construction. Specifically, we use general-domain NER data to train a text NER model. Then, we use the NER model to get coarse-grained named entities on in-domain documents. The results are very noisy due to the wrong boundary or hallucination of the entity. Therefore, we merge similar entities and ask the LLM or human annotators to refine them. We provide instructions for LLM refinement in Table I. Please note that refining the NED is more efficient than labeling named entities sentence by sentence. In practice, we use the LLM-refined NED and human-refined NED in English and Chinese experiments, respectively.

C. Data Augmentation

To generate Spoken NER data, we first sample entities from the NED. In human speech, the distribution of entities is usually sparse and long-tail. Some sentences may contain no entities, and some entities may only appear once in the whole dataset. To achieve better performance on long-tail entities, we try to generate a dataset with balanced entities. As such, we uniformly and randomly sample one or two entities for one sentence (the most common cases) from the NED. After that, we can get the sampled entities $E = \{e_1\}$ or $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$.

TABLE I
INSTRUCTIONS FOR DATA FILTERING IN FIGURE 2 (A) AND DATA GENERATION IN FIGURE 2 (B)

Refine entity	I will write you an entity and its type, you need to judge if it is an entity and the type is correct, print YES or NO. ###User: My entity is ' $\{e_1\}$ ', the type is ' $\{t_1\}$ ' ####Response: ...
Generate text	I want you to act as a speaker in $\{domain\}$. I will write you entities and their type, you need to output a sentence containing these entities. The resulting sentence should be more than 20 words and less than 100 words. ###User: My entities are ' $\{e_1, e_2\}$ ', the types are ' $\{t_1, t_2\}$ ' ####Response: ...

Then we instruct the LLM to act as the speaker in the target domain and generate a sentence containing the sampled entities based on their types. In preliminary studies, we found that TTS models perform badly on very short sentences. Besides, human speakers seldom speak very long sentences. Therefore, we ask the LLM to generate a sentence with 20-100 words. The instructions are provided in Table I. We take the generated sentence as the transcription Y and we can get the BIO tags Z and E2E target \hat{Y} easily by lexical matching.

Finally, we input the generated sentence into a TTS model for generating its speech X . To generate speech with diverse audio features, we randomly choose a speaker of the TTS model and perturb the speaking speed. We further add background noise and simple sound effects to the speech to improve the robustness of Spoken NER models.

D. Noise Filtering

We start with analyzing the noise sources in the generated Spoken NER data: the BIO tags Z , the transcription Y , and the speech X . The generated BIO tags may often go wrong in the following cases: the sampled entity is noisy due to its incomplete or redundant text or wrong type; the LLM generates text without following the required entity type². Due to the satisfying NED and powerful LLM, these errors seldom happen. To confirm that, we manually label 50 random instances for the LLM-refined NED and human-refined NED separately. The two NEDs used in our experiments produce accurate labels, achieving 86% and 96% accuracy, respectively.

The generated text for data augmentation should be fluent and similar to the target distribution; otherwise, it will significantly degrade performance despite the accurate labels. The LLM, trained on extensive and diverse data, is supposed to generate fluent and reasonable text even in specific domains. To examine the assumption, we evaluate the transcription using the language model (LM) in the target domain. The average perplexity of synthetic text is close to real text in the target domain (187.67 vs. 165.55).

Most of the noise is introduced by the TTS model. Usually, the TTS model is evaluated by humans, and it is difficult to automatically evaluate the quality of generated speech [18]. Besides, the evaluation target differs in this task, where we aim to generate speech that an ASR or entity-aware ASR model can recognize. Therefore, we introduce a method similar to round-trip translation for machine translation quality estimation [19]. Specifically, we first use an ASR model to generate the transcription Y' for the speech X , and then we calculate the similarity between Y and Y' using Word Error Rate (WER). With this noise metric, we can filter out the noisy data by simply setting a threshold τ .

²for example, generating "Apple" with the type "fruit" instead of "company".

TABLE II
STATISTICS OF THE AISHELL-NER DATASET AND OUR ANNOTATED ST-CMDS-NER AND CORRESPONDING NED.

Dataset	#Sentence	w/NE	#PER	#LOC	#ORG
AISHELL-NER	120,098	40,839	15,842	20,693	21,455
ST-CMDS-NER	3,000	1,004	700	369	202
ST-CMDS-NED	N/A	N/A	5,741	1,737	1,372

TABLE III
TIME COST OF DIFFERENT DATA ANNOTATION.

	NED	Text NER	ASR	Spoken NER
Num of Entities / Hour	3660	840	180	148

III. NEW BENCHMARK

To the best of our knowledge, AISHELL-NER [8] is the only annotated NER dataset derived from Chinese speech. Based on a public ASR dataset ST-CMDS [20], we introduce a new Spoken NER benchmark ST-CMDS-NER in Chinese. The speech in ST-CMDS mainly focuses on two topics: usual online voice chats and intelligent voice control statements. For construction, we first sample 3,000 sentences from ST-CMDS. Following AISHELL-NER, we annotate three types of named entities for each sentence: PER, LOC, and ORG. As for the construction of our human-annotated NED, we sample other 40,000 sentences from the rest of ST-CMDS and use an NER model trained on AISHELL-NER to predict the named entities. Next, we manually refine these named entities by deleting the non-entity words and correcting the boundary of the wrong entity words. Finally, we get 8,853 entities to build our NED. Besides, the entity overlap between the Spoken NER test set and the NED is 98.70%, which indicates the NED we annotated is of high quality. We also hire eight professional annotators for data labeling work and an expert to sample and check the annotations for quality control. Table II provides detailed information on this benchmark. To estimate the performance of manual annotations, following [21], we select 30% of the data in the dataset for a second annotation. The second pass achieves an F1 score of 92.1% when evaluated against the first pass. This indicates a high degree of consistency in the dataset we annotated. We also measure the efficiency of labeling various types of data (instance per hour) in Table III. Building an NED is approximately 24 times faster than annotating Spoken NER data, indicating that constructing an NED is much more efficient and cost-effective than creating Spoken NER datasets.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Settings

We conduct our experiments in three settings: the in-domain setting, where the in-domain training data is available; the zero-shot domain adaptation setting, where only the source general-domain training data is available; and the fully zero-shot setting, where human-labeled training data is unavailable in both target and general domains. Note that in all three settings, we test our models in the target in-domain test set. Table IV shows all settings and available datasets for training our model.

a) *Data*: In English (En) experiments, we use SLUE-Voxpopuli [21] test set in the European Parliament domain as our test set, which is about 5 hours. In the in-domain setting, we use SLUE-VoxPopuli training set for training, which is about 15 hours. In the domain adaptation setting, we use SLURP [22] with nearly 100 hours of speech as our general-domain dataset. In Chinese (Zh) experiments, we use our annotated benchmark ST-CMDS-NER in the intelligent voice control domain as the test set. In the domain adaptation setting, we use AISHELL-NER as our general-domain dataset, which is

TABLE IV
EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS AND AVAILABLE DATASETS FOR TRAINING OUR MODEL.

Settings	General-domain data (real)	In-domain data (real)	In-domain data (pseudo)
In-domain	×	✓	✓
Zero-shot Domain adaptation	✓	×	✓
Fully zero-shot	×	×	✓

TABLE V
THE PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT SPOKEN NER METHODS IN THE IN-DOMAIN, ZERO-SHOT DOMAIN ADAPTATION, AND FULLY ZERO-SHOT SETTINGS.

Lang	Method	WER↓	Precision↑	Recall↑	F1↑	label-F1↑
En	<i>Pipeline</i>					
	GD [21]	47.48	24.04	8.62	12.69	26.65
	HeardU	<u>18.13</u>	31.16	<u>35.08</u>	33.01	<u>48.26</u>
	GD+ HeardU	20.20	<u>31.45</u>	34.37	<u>33.06</u>	48.14
	ID [21]	12.06	69.32	70.07	69.69	80.50
	ID+Un-Sp [13]	11.52	72.54	68.43	70.43	79.82
	ID+HeardU	11.27	71.14	75.17	73.10	82.62
	<i>E2E</i>					
	GD [21]	52.68	24.14	7.87	11.86	21.47
	HeardU	31.41	36.57	<u>25.70</u>	30.19	41.09
	GD+ HeardU	<u>31.02</u>	<u>42.31</u>	25.24	<u>31.62</u>	<u>41.97</u>
	ID [21]	17.27	70.67	59.36	64.52	73.73
	ID+Un-Sp [13]	14.13	73.81	68.43	71.02	78.43
	ID+HeardU	14.45	77.53	70.37	73.78	79.12
Zh	<i>Pipeline</i>					
	GD [21]	23.73	33.63	26.99	29.94	63.64
	HeardU	30.00	23.66	63.10	34.41	46.73
	GD+ HeardU	22.32	49.34	62.23	55.05	74.67
	<i>E2E</i>					
	GD [21]	27.76	41.05	21.09	27.86	53.64
	HeardU	43.59	27.92	57.20	37.52	49.45
	GD+ HeardU	18.30	72.22	52.56	60.84	69.13

annotated based on AISHELL-1 [23] that contains 170 hours of speech. Note that in this setting, we use the human-refined NED to generate Spoken NER data.

b) *Implementation*: We use gpt-3.5-turbo-0125 as our LLM for text generation and entity refinement in section II. We use Bark-TTS³ and Chat-TTS⁴ as our TTS toolkits for En and Zh speech generation, respectively. We set the noise filter threshold τ to 0.5 for En experiments and 0.3 for Zh experiments. The wav2vec 2.0 base [24] and DeBERTa base [25] are used as the unsupervised pre-trained models. We use the fairseq library [26] to fine-tune wav2vec 2.0 models for the E2E NER and ASR tasks with 80k updates on 100 hours of pseudo-labeled data. We use HuggingFace’s transformers toolkit [27] to train the text NER model on pseudo-labels. Our E2E system uses entity-aware ASR. It adds special tokens to the ASR vocabulary list to identify named entities, *i.e.*, [] for PER, () for LOC, and <> for ORG. Following [21], we use the LM for decoding with beam size 500, LM weight 2, and word insertion penalty -1. All LMs are trained on the corresponding training set in each setting.

c) *Evaluation metrics*: We use WER (%) as the ASR evaluation metric. The WER is calculated based on word- and character-level for En and Zh, respectively. We use F1 (%) and Label-F1 (%) as

³<https://github.com/suno-ai/bark>

⁴<https://github.com/2noise/ChatTTS>

TABLE VI
THE CASES GENERATED BY OUR METHOD.

Entity: Salva Kiir , Type: PER User: {Generate prompt illustrated in Table I} Response: Salva Kiir is a prominent political figure in South Sudan, serving as the country’s president.
Entity: Sakorafa , Type: PER User: Do you understand entity Sakorafa ? Give its meaning. Response: I’m sorry, but “ Sakorafa ” does not appear to be a commonly known entity.
Entity: {Generate prompt illustrated in Table I} Response: Sakorafa has made significant contributions to the field of environmental conservation and sustainable agriculture.

the NER evaluation metrics. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and Label-F1 considers only the tag predictions.

d) *Baselines*: (1) Vanilla Pipeline and E2E methods [21]. In our in-domain setting, the baseline wav2vec 2.0 models are trained using in-domain (ID) human-labeled data. Zero-shot domain adaptation and fully zero-shot settings share the same data, where the models are trained only using general-domain (GD) human-labeled data. (2) Un-Sp [13]. It uses external 100 hours of in-domain speech to enhance the model with distillation; thus, we only compare it in the in-domain setting.

B. Main Results

As shown in Table V, our HeardU outperforms the baselines in all settings. Specifically, HeardU achieves a 32.98% increase in F1 score in the Zh zero-shot domain adaptation setting (GD+HeardU) by using a human-refined high-quality NED. Besides, with an automatically constructed NED, HeardU shows substantial improvements in both En zero-shot domain adaptation (GD+HeardU) (+19.76% F1 scores) and in-domain settings (ID+HeardU) (+2.76% F1 scores). Moreover, our method achieves the SOTA performance in the Label-F1 metric. In the Zh fully zero-shot setting, the HeardU line shows a very high WER, which indicates that the test speech cannot be accurately recognized, thus greatly affecting the final F1 score. This is attributed to the limited capabilities of TTS models and the resulting poor-quality synthetic speech. However, HeardU still outperforms the vanilla domain adaptation method because it identifies more target entities in the test set and achieves higher recall scores.

V. ANALYSIS

A. The Generalization of HeardU

a) *LLM*: Table VI shows several cases generated by the LLM. Note that in the first case, the LLM can generate realistic and fluent sentences using its inherent knowledge of a given entity and type. For the second one, we first ask whether the LLM understands the entity, and then ask the LLM to generate the corresponding sentence given the entity and entity type. The LLM is capable of producing a relevant sentence successfully, as it has encountered a sufficient number of entities in its training data. Even in cases where the LLM has not previously encountered the specific entity, it can generate plausible sentences by inferring meaning based on the entity’s name and type.

b) *TTS*: The TTS model is trained on tens of millions of hours of speech data. For the En, its pronunciation and spelling are strongly related, allowing for the generation of relatively accurate speech from given text. This enables synthesis of the speech of an entity that has never been seen before. Conversely, the structure of the Zh relies on a multitude of characters, most of which can be correctly generated. For extremely rare characters, the TTS system employs a mapping table to

Fig. 3. The performance of our method in the in-domain En setting with different WER thresholds.

TABLE VII
INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT DATA SIZES IN THE IN-DOMAIN EN SETTING.

Data Size	WER↓	Precision↑	Recall↑	F1↑	Label-F1↑
100%	14.45	77.53	70.37	73.78	79.12
75%	14.58	77.20	69.25	73.01	79.30
50%	14.70	76.05	68.03	71.82	78.44
25%	15.15	76.96	63.69	69.70	76.12

convert them into simpler characters with the same pronunciation. In short, the TTS model demonstrates strong generalization capabilities, allowing it to adapt to a wide array of linguistic scenarios.

B. The Impact of Noise Data

We explore the influence of thresholds using WER as the noise metric. As shown in Figure 3, our model performs best with an F1 score of 73.78% when using a WER threshold of 0.5. Note that when the threshold is high, there is too much noisy data in the pseudo-data, which degrades the model’s performance. Conversely, when the threshold is set too low (<0.2), most of the noisy data is filtered out, resulting in overly clean training data that makes the model less robust to the noisy data in the test set. Therefore, taking a relatively intermediate threshold can not only eliminate the excessively noisy part of the pseudo-data, but also retain some noisy data to enhance the robustness of the model.

C. The Impact of Entity Frequency

We analyze the influence of different data sizes, which represent the proportion of entities used. As shown in Table VII, with the decrease in data size, the overall WER does not increase much, but F1 declines greatly. This indicates that reducing the number of instances for each entity has a great impact on the final NER performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

It is challenging even for humans to identify and categorize an unfamiliar entity that they have never heard of. In this paper, we show that constructing and maintaining an NED is feasible. We can present entities in the NED to Spoken NER models by generating synthetic data with LLMs and TTS models. We further analyze the noise in the synthetic data and propose a noise metric for data filtering. We achieve significant improvement across different settings, confirming the flexibility and generalization of the proposed HeardU framework. We hope the released resources will promote further development in this area.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The project was supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 62036004, No. 62276219), Natural Science Foundation of Fujian Province of China (No. 2024J011001), and the Public Technology Service Platform Project of Xiamen (No.3502Z20231043). We also thank the reviewers for their insightful comments.

REFERENCES

- [1] Antoine Caubrie`re, Sophie Rosset, Yannick Este`ve, Antoine Laurent, and Emmanuel Morin. "Where are we in named entity recognition from speech?," in *Proc. of LREC*, 2020.
- [2] Katsuhito Sudoh, Hajime Tsukada, and Hideki Isozaki, "Incorporating speech recognition confidence into discriminative named entity recognition of speech data," in *Proc. of ACL*, 2006, pp. 617–624.
- [3] Christian Raymond, "Robust tree-structured named entities recognition from speech," in *Proc. of ICASSP*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 8475–8479.
- [4] Mohamed Ameur Ben Jannet, Olivier Galibert, Martine Adda-Decker, and Sophie Rosset, "How to evaluate asr output for named entity recognition?," in *Proc. of Interspeech*, 2015, pp. 1289–1293.
- [5] Weitong Ruan, Yaroslav Nechaev, Luoxin Chen, Chengwei Su, and Imre Kiss, "Towards an asr error robust spoken language understanding system," in *Proc. of Interspeech*, Helen Meng, Bo Xu, and Thomas Fang Zheng, Eds., 2020.
- [6] Sahar Ghannay, Antoine Caubrie`re, Yannick Este`ve, Nathalie Camelin, Edwin Simonnet, Antoine Laurent, and Emmanuel Morin, "End-to-end named entity extraction from speech," 2018.
- [7] Hemant Yadav, Sreyan Ghosh, Yi Yu, and Rajiv Ratn Shah, "End-to-end named entity recognition from english speech," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.11184*, 2020.
- [8] Boli Chen, Guangwei Xu, Xiaobin Wang, Pengjun Xie, Meishan Zhang, and Fei Huang, "AISHELL-NER: named entity recognition from chinese speech," in *Proc. of ICASSP*, 2022.
- [9] Siddhant Arora, Siddharth Dalmia, Brian Yan, Florian Metze, Alan W Black, and Shinji Watanabe, "Token-level sequence labeling for spoken language understanding using compositional end-to-end models," in *Proc. of EMNLP Findings*, Yoav Goldberg, Zornitsa Kozareva, and Yue Zhang, Eds., 2022.
- [10] Ido Cohn, Itay Laish, Genady Beryozkin, Gang Li, Izhak Shafran, Idan Szpektor, Tzvika Hartman, Avinatan Hassidim, and Yossi Matias, "Audio de-identification: A new entity recognition task," *Proc. of NAACL-HLT*, 2019.
- [11] Min Zhang, Xiaosong Qiao, Yanqing Zhao, Chang Su, Yinglu Li, Yuang Li, Ming Zhu, Mengyao Piao, Song Peng, Shimin Tao, et al., "Knowledge prompt for whisper: An asr entity correction approach with knowledge base," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData)*, 2023.
- [12] Quentin Meeus, Marie-Francine Moens, et al., "Msner: A multilingual speech dataset for named entity recognition," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.11519*, 2024.
- [13] Bangyi Yang. Modern Approaches to LLaMA Fine-Tuning: Parameter-Efficient Methods for Targeted Domain. TechRxiv. DOI: 10.36227/techrxiv.176827298.88219560/v1. 2025.
- [14] Ankita Pasad, Felix Wu, Suwon Shon, Karen Livescu, and Kyu Han, "On the use of external data for spoken named entity recognition," in *Proc. of NAACL-HLT*, Marine Carpuat, Marie-Catherine de Marneffe, and Iva`n Vladimir Meza Ru`iz, Eds., 2022.
- [15] Chris Hokamp and Qun Liu, "Lexically constrained decoding for sequence generation using grid beam search," 2017.
- [16] J Edward Hu, Huda Khayrallah, Ryan Culkin, Patrick Xia, Tongfei Chen, Matt Post, and Benjamin Van Durme, "Improved lexically constrained decoding for translation and monolingual rewriting," in *Proc. of NAACL-HLT*, 2019.
- [17] Jiwei Li, Michel Galley, Chris Brockett, Jianfeng Gao, and William B Dolan, "A diversity-promoting objective function for neural conversation models," in *Proc. of NAACL-HLT*, Kevin Knight, Ani Nenkova, and Owen Rambow, Eds., 2016.
- [18] Zhiheng Huang, Wei Xu, and Kai Yu, "Bidirectional lstm-crf models for sequence tagging," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1508.01991*, 2015.
- [19] Xu Tan, Jiawei Chen, Haohe Liu, Jian Cong, Chen Zhang, Yanqing Liu, Xi Wang, Yichong Leng, Yuanhao Yi, Lei He, et al., "Naturalspeech: End-to-end text-to-speech synthesis with human-level quality," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 2024.
- [20] Jihyung Moon, Naver Papago, Hyunchang Cho, and Eunjeong L Park, "Revisiting round-trip translation for quality estimation," in *Proc. of EAMT*, 2020.
- [21] Surfingtech, "St-cmds-20170001 1, free st chinese mandarin corpus," 2017.
- [22] Suwon Shon, Ankita Pasad, Felix Wu, Pablo Brusco, Yoav Artzi, Karen Livescu, and Kyu J Han, "Slue: New benchmark tasks for spoken language understanding evaluation on natural speech," in *Proc. of ICASSP*, 2022.
- [23] Emanuele Bastianelli, Andrea Vanzo, Pawel Swietojanski, and Verena Rieser, "SLURP: A spoken language understanding resource package," in *Proc. of EMNLP*, Bonnie Webber, Trevor Cohn, Yulan He, and Yang Liu, Eds., 2020.
- [24] Hui Bu, Jiayu Du, Xingyu Na, Bengu Wu, and Hao Zheng, "AISHELL-1: an open-source mandarin speech corpus and a speech recognition baseline," in *20th Conference of the Oriental Chapter of the International Coordinating Committee on Speech Databases and Speech I/O Systems and Assessment, O-COCOSDA 2017, Seoul, South Korea, November 1-3, 2017*, 2017, IEEE.
- [25] Alexei Baevski, Yuhao Zhou, Abdelrahman Mohamed, and Michael Auli, "wav2vec 2.0: A framework for self-supervised learning of speech representations," in *Proc. of NeurIPS*, Hugo Larochelle, Marc`Aurelio Ranzato, Raia Hadsell, Maria-Florina Balcan, and Hsuan-Tien Lin, Eds., 2020.
- [26] Pengcheng He, Xiaodong Liu, Jianfeng Gao, and Weizhu Chen, "Deberta: decoding-enhanced bert with disentangled attention," in *Proc. of ICLR*, 2021.
- [27] Myle Ott, Sergey Edunov, Alexei Baevski, Angela Fan, Sam Gross, Nathan Ng, David Grangier, and Michael Auli, "Proc. of naacl-hlt," 2019.
- [28] Thomas Wolf, Lysandre Debut, Victor Sanh, Julien Chaumond, Clement Delangue, Anthony Moi, Pierric Cistac, Tim Rault, Re`mi Louf, Morgan Funtowicz, Joe Davison, Sam Shleifer, Patrick von Platen, Clara Ma, Yacine Jernite, Julien Plu, Canwen Xu, Teven Le Scao, Sylvain Gugger, Mariama Drame, Quentin Lhoest, and Alexander M. Rush, "Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing," in *Proc. of EMNLP*, Qun Liu and David Schlangen, Eds., 2020.